

IMPORTANCE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF USING NEW METHODS IN ENGLISH FOR STUDENTS OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6536030>

Eronova Umida Mirzakulovna

*Surkhandarya region, Muzrabot district
Primary school English teacher of 8th grade*

Annotation: *Improving the modern goals, content and technologies of teaching English in primary education, a textbook that serves to generalize the traditional and foreign experience gained in the practice of teaching English to primary school students. Due to the lack of applications, insufficient efficiency is achieved in the training of teachers for this field. This article describes the importance and features of the use of new methods in English for primary school students.*

Keywords: *Method, innovation, method, didactic games, interactive method, education.*

Today, about 60 percent of the world's population is two or more. Everyone knows that they can speak different languages. Globalization processes in the world acceleration, transition to free market relations, and high productivity encouraging the introduction of technology into 'linguistic capital', i.e. foreign the need for professionals who are fluent in languages (especially English) intensifies. After the independence of our country, the interest of young people in learning foreign languages has increased, and the state creates many opportunities for language learning. As the first President Islam Karimov said: "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, which seeks to take its rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. " One of the decisions that led to positive changes is the Resolution of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No PP-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages." Under the leadership of the Coordinating Council for the Further Development of Foreign Language Learning, a large-scale work has begun in all areas of education. For example, from the 2013-

2014 academic year, general education in the first grades of their schools, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of play-type lessons and oral speech lessons was established. Textbooks and teaching aids for these classes have also been created. It is noteworthy that the activities in the complexes designed for first-graders are proportional to the age of the little ones. The children began their first acquaintance with a foreign language by learning the culture of greeting, colors, and everyday words in the form of dialogue. According to the decision, to teach foreign languages, mainly English from primary school, to further increase their interest in teaching foreign languages, English lessons in all secondary schools from 1st grade in the form of various fun games teaching and at the same time developing students' oral speech, and from the 2nd grade onwards, the transition to modern, innovative methods of teaching the alphabet, reading and grammar began in stages. Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing dramatically. This is because it is becoming increasingly difficult to live without knowing English in the process of life. But language learning also depends on age. In fact, scientists have proven that children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn a language, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, children spend more time than adults and memorize the information they learn quickly.

Undoubtedly, equipping foreign language classrooms in our country's educational institutions with modern information and communication technologies and advanced teaching aids, broadcasting programs on television and radio to teach children and adolescents in foreign languages, the history of other countries and Regular screenings of popular science and popular foreign feature films and cartoons with Uzbek subtitles on culture, world science and technology have allowed our youth to get acquainted with the past, culture and science of the peoples of the world. In teaching foreign languages to students in primary school, especially in the first grade, it is necessary to take into account the age, physiological, psychological characteristics of the student. As noted in the resolution, the implementation of foreign language teaching in the form of play-style lessons and oral speech lessons in the first grades is indeed appropriate for younger students. The use of game technology in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their thinking, worldview, thinking expands. Scholars have argued that a play-based approach to education facilitates the learning process. Not only does it make it easier, but it also increases the child's interest in science and encourages the child to gain in-depth knowledge. Play-style

lessons help children develop oral speech. First graders love a variety of pictures or videos. Through different colored pictures, games should be used regularly to enhance their speech. During the game, children should be encouraged to remember words and pronounce them correctly. . As children's vocabulary increases, other types of games, as well as the organization of various competitions, are also important. Children can first complete exercises on topics such as "Vegetable Names" and "Pets" through games. Then, when they are displayed in accordance with the colorful images on the computer, students' speech develops and their range of attitudes to the environment expands. During the presentation of a new topic, words and pictures will appear on the screen. Students will be able to listen to words and pronounce them. The principle of individualization of education should be taken into account when presenting the topic on a computer. Some students have difficulty perceiving a graphic word and some a sound image. The computer helps students to identify and overcome difficulties in learning English by overcoming this or that difficulty through exercises. It is also possible to organize other educational games aimed at mastering grammar from the second grade. For example, interesting games such as "Who is literate?", "Who is smart?", "Who am I?", "Chain", "Role play", "Find the word". "Who is smart? "The game gives good results in increasing spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard, and the words are written correctly and incorrectly. Students are asked to find the misspelled word and spell it correctly. The winner of the game is determined by which student spells the misspelled words correctly and first. We know that in the current educational process, the student must be the subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase learning effectiveness. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach independent thinking. Today, English language teachers in the United States, based on the experience of English educators, use the following innovative methods:

"Merry riddles" Teach students puzzles. It is important in teaching English that they learn words that are unfamiliar to them and find the answer to the riddle. Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. (Warm-up exercises) Use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson. Pantomime can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises. The A chain story method helps students to improve their speaking and memory. Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. helps to develop zaki speech, for which it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic. Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students, allowing all students to attend class at the same time, which saves time.

In the "Find the place of the word" game, the words are swapped and the sentence is formed by putting the words in the right place. The "Collection" game is held to reinforce students' knowledge of a specific topic. The game is organized in the form of a row competition or work in small groups. For example, groups are given a task to find the words that represent the sign. The team that finds the most points in the allotted time wins. Cartoons. Although children do not understand the words in the cartoon while learning a foreign language, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language. Children are taught everything from English songs to poems, stories and videos.

It should also be noted that children aged 6-7 years do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. That is why it is important not to start teaching grammar to elementary school students who are learning English. Otherwise, the first step in learning a foreign language can be tiring for the child and weaken his or her interest in learning the language. Because it is difficult to teach a foreign language to primary school students, it is also one of the responsible tasks. Therefore, the following innovative methods can be used to teach English to primary school students in a meaningful and interesting way:

- Visual recall. It is known that young children have heard remembers the objects he sees more than his data. Therefore, the lesson is taught through a variety of visual aids, posters, visual and commonly used objects, teaching new words by writing on objects and composing sentences with the participation of new words learned . For example, writing a flower, a bird, a watch, a car, the sun, and so on. Because such items, which are often used in daily life, are constantly in sight and in constant use, the child learns these words involuntarily.

- TO includes most of the games that help you master competitive grammar and vocabulary. In doing so, the children perform a variety of tasks given by the teacher. As a result, there is competition among students and their interest in language learning increases. Indeed, as Chinese thinkers have said, "All human interests are created through competition."

- Sing and compose words that are difficult to understand or remember through music. In addition to memorizing new words, the child's oral speech also develops. For example, it can be shown that children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing.

- Learning through fun games; The role of teaching through a variety of games in teaching English is invaluable. Playing a variety of games throughout the lesson will further increase the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom,

encouraging even inactive students to participate better in the lessons. The following games are an example of our word.

- Mixed technique where we can voluntarily combine different techniques. For example, children can play games, sing songs, draw pictures, and demonstrate new words through a variety of actions. The advantage of the technique is in the variety. In doing so, the reader is not limited to just one thing.

- “Merry Riddles” (Merry Riddles) Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English so that they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle.

- "Pantomime" (pantomime). In doing so, the teacher says a word to the students and the student points to it. The rest of the students will have to find the word and say the English name.

- Learning through the senses (tasting vegetables, fruits, food, touching various objects, smelling flowers). Before exploring this new method, one should cite the views of a practicing psychologist: it should even try to involve the sense of smell and taste in the process of remembering”.

- Teaching through cartoons. It is known that children are interested in watching different cartoons. In the process of watching cartoons in English, he tries to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters, even though he does not understand the words in the cartoon. This is a fun and effective way for children to learn the language.

The difference between English and other disciplines in the education system is that it is both an educational goal and an educational tool. While the acquisition of speaking skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing) in English is an educational goal, the language being studied also acquires the status of a means of obtaining and conveying new and useful information. The importance of using modern, new methods, especially in this subject, is that it helps students to easily master the language and keep it in their memory.

In conclusion, it is important to note that the use of new methods in the English language is very important. In teaching English, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, their interest in learning a foreign language, the development of modern didactic developments based on pedagogical technologies that help to fully meet the needs and develop a robust mechanism for their implementation. provides a practical solution.

REFERENCES:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No PP-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages."
2. Iriskulov AT and others Kids 'English pupil's book 2nd grade –Tashkent —Uzbekistan; 2014
3. Turdaliyeva. G "Modern approaches and innovations in teaching English in primary school"
4. Tajibayev G.S "Teaching English in primary school" - Namangan, 2019
5. Hoshimov O. Yakubov I. Methods of teaching English. T., - 2003

